

Sustainability assessment of advanced calcium looping solutions for the decarbonization of the iron and steel industry

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Pathways to decarbonize the iron and steel industrial sector with low-carbon solutions.
- LCA methodology used to assess traditional vs. advanced CaL-based system designs.
- Advanced CaL solutions cuts over 60% GWP at EAF-based steel plants.
- Ca(OH)₂ use and CPU vent gas recirculation drive major efficiency gains.
- Onshore pipeline and offshore CO₂ shipping add 18.85 kg_{CO2} eq./t_{CO2} captured to total GWP.

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Iron and steel industry
Electric arc furnace
Life cycle assessment
Calcium looping
Ca(OH)₂ injection
CO₂ capture and transportation

ABSTRACT

Achieving the 1.5°C climate target by 2050 requires urgent action in the steelmaking sector, as it contributes by about 7% to global CO₂ emissions. With Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) routes representing 30% of global production, their decarbonization is critical to sector-wide emission reductions. The current study evaluates the environmental implications of an EAF equipped with a Calcium Looping (CaL) based carbon capture unit via Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. The environmental analysis follows a cradle-to-gate approach and it is conducted using the ReCiPe 2016 assessment method. Four distinct CaL configurations featuring variations such as intermediate solid storage and/or calcium hydroxide, Ca(OH)₂, injection were investigated, each assessed under two alternative CO₂ transportation scenarios: T1 – onshore pipeline followed by offshore shipping, and T2 – onshore truck transportation followed by offshore shipping. The findings suggest more than 63% Global Warming Potential (GWP) reduction in the advanced CaL configurations as against standard strategies, primarily due to Ca(OH)₂ injection (i.e., enhanced CO₂ capture efficiency) and CO₂ purification unit (CPU) vent gas recirculation. However, these improvements are offset by higher impacts in Fossil Depletion Potential (FDP), Mineral Depletion Potential (MDP), Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem (POFP_{ecosystem}), Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human health (POFP_{human-health}), Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP), and Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (TETP). Of the two CO₂ transportation pathways, T1 and T2 show similar values in five indicators (i.e., Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential – FETP, Freshwater Eutrophication Potential – FEP, Human Toxicity Potential cancer – HTP_{cancer}, MDP, and HTP_{non-cancer}), yet T1 outperforms T2 in terms of GWP, FDP, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP. Of all scenarios, the advanced CaL configuration with two intermediate storage tanks coupled with T1 exhibits the best overall environmental performance. A detailed analysis reveals that the CO₂ transportation contributes around 16.8 kg_{CO2} eq./t_{CO2} captured, emphasizing the importance of developing alternative transport strategies to reduce associated emissions.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2026.148761>

Received 8 September 2025; Received in revised form 19 February 2026; Accepted 11 June 2026

Available online 14 June 2026

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1. Introduction

As industrialization progressed, carbon dioxide emissions have continuously increased, thus accelerating climate change, hence global warming, a growing concern that calls for collective global action (Li et al., 2025). Energy-intensive industrial processes must undergo deep decarbonization in order to meet the environmental targets outlined in the Net Zero Emission (NZE) Scenario (Rahnama Mobarakeh and Kienberger, 2022). Despite a reduction in emissions both in 2020 and 2022, additional efforts are necessary to address emissions intensity. According to the report published by the International Energy Agency (IEA), the industrial sector was responsible for over 35% of global energy consumption in 2022. Over the past decade, the continuous growth in production in high energy-consuming sectors, including iron and steel, cement, chemical and petrochemical, as well as pulp and paper, has significantly contributed to the increasing demand for energy (IEA - International Energy Agency). In addition, it has been reported that one-fourth of the CO₂ emissions in 2022 (about 9.0 Gt of CO₂) were produced by the industrial sector (Min et al., 2022). Of total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, a substantial amount stems from the on-site combustion of fossil sources used for energy generation. Nonetheless, additional releases also arise from core manufacturing processes or due to unavoidable chemical transformations – such as those occurring in metallurgical operations (IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change et al., 2023).

Among the industrial subsectors producing various materials, steel remains one of the most essential materials worldwide, with global annual production reaching approximately 1.96 billion tons, with a CO₂ intensity of 1.92 tons of CO₂ per ton of steel produced (World Steel Association, 2025). Currently, the steel subsector ranks as the second-largest energy consumer (Chisalita et al., 2019) and contributes by roughly 11% of total direct and indirect CO₂ emissions (Wells et al., 2025), primarily driven by fossil fuel-based production processes (Perpiñán et al., 2023).

Currently, steel production follows two main pathways: primary production from iron ore and secondary production based on the recovery and reuse of steel scrap (Carbone et al., 2023). Primary steel-making, performed employing traditional technologies, remains substantially more demanding in terms of energy and CO₂ emissions as opposed to secondary production (Scaccabarozzi et al., 2024). There are two process alternatives under the primary manufacturing route: one involves the use of a Blast Furnace combined with a Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF), while the other employs a Direct Iron Reduction furnace with an Electric Arc Furnace (DRI-EAF). Secondary production entails scrap-based steel production by means of EAF (Boldrini et al., 2024).

In accordance with the reported data, over 70% of the energy requirements and feedstock needed in this sector are met by coking coal (Nurdiawati et al., 2025). The BF uses about 75% of total energy intake, with the remaining portion providing heat at the sinter and coking facilities (Kim et al., 2022). Compared to the BF-BOF route, both scrap-based EAF and DRI-EAF technologies offer a significant reduction in terms of CO₂ emissions, along with lower energy consumption – for example, energy uses range from 4 to 6 GJ/t in the scrap-EAF, 10 GJ/t in the DRI-EAF, and 13 – 14 GJ/t in the BF-BOF (Perpiñán et al., 2023). Despite its large energy consumption and high GHG emissions, around 71% of the world's steel is produced through the BF-BOF route, while the remaining is produced via EAF routes (scrap-based EAF and DRI-EAF) (Kildahl et al., 2023). This is primarily due to the lower cost of coal, the constrained supply of scrap metal, and the high infrastructure costs needed to integrate renewable power into the EAF route (Wang et al., 2025).

The integration of Best Available Techniques (BAT) is regarded as one of the key measures to mitigate CO₂ emissions in the short-term (Scaccabarozzi et al., 2025). Additional strategies for reducing GHG releases include shifting from coke and coal to alternative fuels, such as

H₂ (Shahabuddin et al., 2023), and enhancing overall thermal efficiency (Zhang et al., 2021). Bonacina et al. (2024) looked at various EAF plant configurations that, besides steel, are able to produce electricity, H₂, and methanol through incorporating technologies such as oxy-post-combustion, carbon capture, high-temperature electrolysis or co-electrolysis.

Nevertheless, in the medium to long term, Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage (CCUS) implementation stands as a key strategy to decarbonize the steel industry and achieve maximum impact (Garcia and Berghout, 2019). Across different CCUS options (i.e., pre-combustion, oxy-combustion, etc.), post-combustion CO₂ capture is regarded as the most appropriate option (Sedransk Campbell et al., 2017). Furthermore, a range of post-combustion technologies, currently at different levels of development, are available for potential application (i.e., absorption, adsorption, and membrane separation) (Cormos, 2025a).

Several studies have evaluated the technical, economic, and environmental performance of integrating CCUS systems into the steel industry. Zecca et al. (2025) introduced a novel CO₂ capture concept based on a multicolumn swing principle, emphasizing its much lower costs compared to conventional amine scrubbing. Despite that, at present, the most mature option is based on post-combustion capture using alkanolamines (i.e., Mono-Ethanol-Amine (MEA)). Cormos (2025b) examined the techno-economic and environmental performance of a 100 MW solar-driven calcium looping (CaL) power plant with thermochemical energy storage, reporting high net efficiency (>40%), competitive capital intensity, and overall low environmental impacts. Li et al. (2024) performed a LCA comparing conventional hot braising and CCUS-based carbonation treatments of steel slag, demonstrating that the carbonation route reduced global warming potential (GWP) by a net impact of –76.78 kg CO₂ eq. per ton of steel slag. Arasto et al. (2013) evaluated different post-combustion CO₂ capture approaches to mitigate GHG emissions at an integrated steel mill and proved that between 50 and 75% emissions reduction would be feasible. Luca and Petrescu (2021) explored the environmental impact of integrating amine-scrubbing, membrane CO₂ capture, and various O₂ separation methods in the iron and steel industry, concluding that membrane-based CO₂ capture offers clear advantages over gas-liquid absorption. Mio et al. (2022) investigated three CO₂ capture methods, Methyl-Di-Ethanol-Amine (MDEA), sodium hydroxide, and membrane, highlighting sodium bicarbonate formation as a key step towards decarbonizing the steel sector. Perpiñán et al. (2023) performed a techno-economic analysis to assess the feasibility of combining reactive gas-liquid CO₂ capture with the concept of Power-to-Gas (PtG) within the iron and steel sector. Rigamonti and Brivio (2022) assessed the environmental performance of an integrated system converting steel mill off-gases into methanol and electricity, proving that avoided production credits outweigh process-related burdens in 12 of the 17 assessed impact categories.

Yang et al. (2023) evaluated the integration of the amine-scrubbing within the iron and steel industry through techno-economic and exergy analyses, and concluded that exergy destruction reduction should prioritize the absorber unit, while exergy loss mitigation should target the flash and stripper units. Wells et al. (2025) examined various flue gas compositions aiming to determine the optimal liquid-to-gas (L/G) and solvent-to-CO₂ ratios, with the goal of minimizing the specific reboiler duty for typical flue gases from steel production. Moreover, ADNOC Al-Reyadah plant in Abu Dhabi is the only large-scale steel facility operating with a CCUS system, employing a gas-liquid absorption process with a total capacity of 800 kt of CO₂ per year (Global CCS Institute, 2025).

Despite its maturity, major drawbacks are directly associated with amine-sweetening, including high energy costs for the solvent regeneration, equipment-related concerns due to the solvent's corrosive nature, and high vapor pressure (Aghel et al., 2022). Calcium Looping (CaL) process is regarded as one of the most promising and cost-efficient post-combustion CCUS technologies, though it has yet to be

implemented at full industrial scale (Papalas et al., 2024). In recent years, CaL has made significant progress, achieving megawatt-scale operation through various reactor designs (De Lena et al., 2022). In addition, Arias et al. (2024) demonstrated a novel strategy enabling near-complete CO₂ capture in the carbonator (>99%), while highlighting enhanced fuel flexibility through the use of biomass in an oxy-fired circulating fluidized bed (CFB) calciner. Moreover, even though research focused on the implementation of CaL in large point sources, Criado et al. (2024) proposed a decoupled CaL approach, which may be integrated at a lower industrial scale. Cormos (2016) compared chemical absorption with CaL for CO₂ capture, concluding that CaL offers significant benefits. Chisalita et al. (2019) conducted a cradle-to-gate life cycle assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental performance of a MEA-based configuration against the CaL system. The authors found that CaL exhibits better performance in eight out of ten impact categories studied. Carbone et al. (2023) focused on various integration scenarios for CaL within both BF-BOF and DRI-EAF steel-making pathways, concluding that the DRI-EAF route offers a lower carbon footprint. In a recent study, Shu et al. (2025) explored a novel system consisting of a solar-assisted chemical looping gasification for DRI production, employing syngas derived from biomass as the reducing medium. Jeswani et al. (2025) compared the environmental impact of an innovative decarbonization method focused on the Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU) – chemical looping coupled with reverse water-gas shift reaction and Fischer-Tropsch synthesis – against MDEA-based pre-combustion carbon capture scenario.

Current literature reveals a significant absence of LCA-based evaluations focused on decarbonization approaches for EAF steel production. The majority of the existing studies predominantly target traditional BF-BOF pathways, with investigations focused on integrating the steel-making sector with post-combustion CCUS systems, such as amine scrubbing, or renewable DRI processes. As a result, the environmental performance of decarbonization options specific to EAF plants remains underexplored. To address this gap, the current study conducts a comprehensive LCA of four CaL-based case studies that specifically target EAF steel plants, each coupled with two alternative scenarios for the CO₂ transport in the region of Mo i Rana, Norway.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. General description of the investigated cases

A steelmaking plant based on the EAF was used as a reference for the present study. In particular, the CaL technology is applied to treat the off-gas generated from the EAF, while other production units are not considered. The EAF has a production capacity of 112 t_{HM}/h, while it consumes 50 – 70 MW of electric power and 3000 – 5000 Nm³/h O₂. Besides, its average CO₂ emissions are estimated at 92 kt/y. Due to the batch-wise operation of the EAF process, the generated off-gas exhibits highly variable properties over time. The maximum, average, and minimum values of CO₂ content, flow rate, and temperature of the EAF off-gas are reported in Table 1. Moreover, the complete profiles of the EAF off-gas properties are reported in Montiel-Bohórquez et al. (2025).

The standard CO₂ capture plant based on the CaL technology, designed to capture CO₂ from flue gases with no (or small) variability, typically consists of a calciner, a carbonator, a steam power cycle, a CO₂

Table 1
Range and average value for the main properties of the EAF off-gas (Montiel-Bohórquez et al., 2025).

Property	Range	Average
Flow rate [m ³ /h]	4.0 – 224.0	64.00
CO ₂ content [vol%]	0.0 – 25.0	8.00
CO ₂ molar flow [kmol/s]	0.0 – 0.33	0.07
Temperature [°C]	174 – 1190	730

purification unit (CPU), and an Air Separation Unit (ASU). However, for systems handling fluctuating flue gases, such as those produced by EAF steelmaking, strategies to enhance flexibility should be incorporated to guarantee operability and performance. Consequently, the implementation of the following additional process units is considered for the CaL plant configurations analyzed in the present work:

- An EAF off-gas cooler, to control the temperature ($\leq 400^\circ\text{C}$) at the inlet of the carbonator blower;
- An adiabatic, isothermal carbonator (620°C) with an external fluidized bed heat exchanger to control the temperature of solids entering the reactor. In addition, the possibility of CO₂-depleted gas recirculation to sustain the carbonator's fluidisation velocity above 3 m/s;
- A heat recovery system based on a solar salt loop with thermal energy storage (TES), to decouple the steam power cycle from the time-variable high temperature thermal power from the CaL reactors and off-gas cooler;
- Two fluid storages are included for: i) liquid O₂ produced by the ASU at a constant rate, and ii) CO₂-rich gas produced by the calciner at a variable rate. With this, both ASU and CPU are decoupled from fluctuations and operate at full load.
- An additional strategy is proposed to further improve calciner operation in the CaL plant. This includes two storage vessels for solids produced by the carbonator and the calciner. By doing so, it is possible to control the solids flow rate going to each reactor and to buffer the variability of the solids composition from the carbonator operating at variable load.

In addition to the challenges of operating the CaL plant to capture CO₂ from fluctuating EAF off-gas, another challenge is maximizing the CO₂ capture rate (CCR). The first barrier to achieving higher CCR values is the maximum CO₂ capture efficiency attainable in the carbonator, which is expected to be below 90% for the carbonator operating at temperatures above 600°C and relatively low CO₂ concentrations (8% on average for the EAF flue gases in this work). A potential solution to improve the CO₂ capture efficiency is implementing a second CO₂ capture zone downstream the carbonator cyclone, where the cooled CO₂-depleted gas (550°C) from the carbonator is put in contact with injected Ca(OH)₂ particles for further CO₂ capture; Ca(OH)₂ is used due to the better sorbent performance at low temperatures, compared to CaO (Arias et al., 2022a; Criado et al., 2018). The second barrier to higher CCR values arises from the CO₂ released by the CPU in the vent gas, which is estimated to account for 4 – 5% of total CO₂ entering the capture plant (including EAF flue gases, fuel, and limestone). Thus, this CO₂ loss may be avoided by recirculating the CPU vent gas to the carbonator.

Four cases were investigated to analyze the performance of the CaL-based CO₂ capture plants incorporating the different flexibility-improving strategies described above. Each case includes a distinct combination of the strategies presented above, as reported in Table 2.

A brief description of the processes taking place in the CaL plant, which applies to all the investigated cases, is provided in the following paragraph. This description is intended to highlight the main operating parameters of the plant configurations, while the detailed description of the flexible CaL system is available in Montiel-Bohórquez et al. (2025).

Fig. 1 illustrates the scheme of the CaL plant. As previously presented, the CaL plant comprises the (A) EAF off-gas cooling section, the (B) CaL section (calciner, carbonator, and optional solid storage), the (E) CPU, the (F) ASU, the (C) heat recovery and thermal energy storage system, and the (D) power production system.

The hot flue gas from the EAF is directed into the flue gas cooler (A) to lower its temperature. Within this unit, the sensible heat of the gas is absorbed by the cold heat-transfer fluid (HTF – solar salt). The cooled off-gas then enters the CaL section (B), where it reacts with the solid sorbent to capture CO₂, producing a CO₂-lean gas stream that exits the

Table 2
Cases analyzed and the strategies included in each of them.

Case	Strategies A-D	Intermediate solid storage	Ca(OH) ₂ injection + CPU vent gas recirculation
NST-STD	✓	✗	✗
NST-ADV	✓	✗	✓
2ST-STD	✓	✓	✗
2ST-ADV	✓	✓	✓

NST: No intermediate solid storage, **2ST:** Two intermediate solid storage, **STD:** standard configuration with no Ca(OH)₂ injection nor CPU vent gas recirculation, **ADV:** advanced configuration with Ca(OH)₂ injection and CPU vent gas recirculation.

Fig. 1. Simplified block diagram of the CaL-based carbon capture system.

Note: Dashed lines for “solid purge” and “CPU vent” indicate that the fate of this stream depends on the case analyzed (see Table 2). A more detailed process diagram is provided in the Supplementary Material File.

system and the carbonated sorbent that is subsequently regenerated in the calciner. Sorbent regeneration is driven by combusting fuel (residual forestry biomass) to achieve the target calcination temperature (920°C). Fuel combustion in the calciner is conducted with a mixture of oxygen (95 wt% purity) and recirculated CO₂-rich gas. Therefore, an ASU (F) is included to produce the demanded O₂; furthermore, O₂ is stored as a liquid before being supplied to the reactor at a variable rate based on the calciner demand. To maintain system efficiency, fresh limestone is fed into the calciner to compensate for the solid purge removed from the process. The solid purge can exit the system as a by-product of the process (cases without Ca(OH)₂ injection) or be recirculated to the hydrator to produce Ca(OH)₂ (cases with Ca(OH)₂ injection in the polishing zone).

The CO₂-rich gas from sorbent regeneration is routed to intermediate storage and subsequently processed in the CPU (E) to remove impurities, yielding purified CO₂ ready for transportation. Similar to the solid purge, the CPU vent can be released to the atmosphere or recirculated to the carbonator (CaL section, B) to maximize the overall CO₂ capture rate. Heat generated within the CaL section (B) and flue gas cooler (A) is recovered by heating cold HTF from the TES (C). Then, the hot HTF is

exploited to generate steam, which drives the Steam Cycle (D) to produce electricity.

For the cases with Ca(OH)₂ injection, the off-gas is cooled to 500°C before entering the second CO₂ capture zone (polishing zone) to reduce the equilibrium CO₂ partial pressure and increase the amount of CO₂ that can be captured before reaching the thermodynamic limit. Based on the results from the drop-tube experiments reported by Borja Arias et al., 2022b, Ca(OH)₂-to-CO₂ molar ratios close to 1.5 – 1.7 are feasible due to the fast kinetics and carrying capacity of the hydrated Ca-sorbent particles, allowing for conversion of 0.6 – 0.7 mol/mol in a few seconds. Nonetheless, due to the lack of conclusive experimental evidence at large scales, a conservative Ca(OH)₂-to-CO₂ molar ratio of 3.0 (equivalent to a sorbent conversion of around 0.33) is used in this study, which aligns with Ca-to-CO₂ molar ratios reported in previous conceptual studies where the injection of Ca(OH)₂ was also investigated to improve the capture efficiency of CaL (Secomandi et al., 2024). On the other hand, optimization of Ca(OH)₂ injection (and the associated energy and material consumption) would require a more detailed analysis using dedicated modelling tools and extensive experimental data, which are beyond the scope of this work.

2.2. LCA of the evaluated scenarios

LCA is a well-established methodological framework for evaluating a wide range of environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product's or process's life cycle, thus offering a comprehensive perspective (Li et al., 2022). In addition, LCA has increasingly gained relevance as a key tool in industrial product development, supporting the evaluation and prioritization of much greener alternatives while ensuring system efficiency within specific limitations (Rihner et al., 2025). The current investigation follows the framework and guidelines provided by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) via ISO 14040 (2006) (i.e., principles and framework) and ISO 14044 (2006) (i.e., requirements and guidelines). Therefore, the present study aims to quantify and evaluate the environmental performance of a CaL-based post-combustion CO₂ capture system employed to treat the off-gas released from an EAF. The system function performance is evaluated and quantified by the functional unit (FU), which also acts as a standard for the input and output streams. One ton of CO₂ captured was defined as the FU for the current investigation.

System boundary definition may follow one of four standard methodologies: i) cradle-to-gate, ii) cradle-to-grave, iii) gate-to-gate, iv) and gate-to-grave. In the context of this study, a cradle-to-gate perspective has been selected as it accounts for the entire CO₂ capture process, from the upstream supply chain of raw materials up to the delivery of the final product. Fig. 2 illustrates the system boundaries, which include: 1) upstream processes: electricity and/or fuel generation, limestone sourcing and transport up to the plant gate, O₂ generation from an ASU, flue gas generation from the EAF; 2) main process: CaL-based CO₂ capture unit, including purification and compression (CPU); and 3) downstream processes: wastewater treatment, solid waste disposal, and transport of the captured CO₂.

Geographical location and temporal system boundaries represent two of the most critical parameters in defining the analytical framework of an LCA, particularly within the iron and steel industrial sector (Nurdiawati et al., 2025). The geographic boundary is primarily influenced by the market dynamics and product specifications, as the physical location of the plant shapes both resource availability and distribution pathways. In contrast, defining temporal boundaries poses greater challenges, as certain life cycle stages, including end-of-life disposal or potential reuse – must be projected into the future and are therefore subject to uncertainty. For the purpose of this investigation, it is presumed that the plant is located in Mo i Rana, Norway, and that it will remain operational for a duration of 25 years. When required, the electricity demand is assumed to be met by the national power grid.

The assumptions considered for the limestone sourcing and

transportation, as well as the assumptions used in the main CaL-based unit, are reported in Tables 3 and 4.

The nearest storage location for the captured CO₂ is the Melkøya terminal and the two transportation scenarios detailed in Table 5 entail onshore transportation to the port via either pipelines (T1) or trucks (T2), followed by offshore transportation via ships. Following the CaL-based capture unit, CO₂ is compressed within the CPU to 110 bar; the transportation-related data account for the energy consumption associated with the CO₂ in this compressed state. Reconditioning for injection is not considered here. For a better representation, the two scenarios taken into consideration for the CO₂ transport are graphically illustrated in Fig. 3.

In practice, it is not always viable to integrate all initially intended elements into an LCA investigation. Adjusting the defined goal and scope to accommodate newly available data is frequently unjustified, and thus, it is essential to identify and explain any system exclusions (Curran, 2017). The boundaries of the current research omit some elements, which are considered beyond the scope of the analysis: i) the construction and dismantling phases of the facility; ii) ongoing maintenance and repair activities, iii) the construction of transportation infrastructure, including roads, railways, and marine vessels, iv) the installation of unloading equipment and facilities, v) human labor inputs, and vi) rare and unpredictable events such as accidental leaks or unplanned releases.

The present analysis relies on both primary data, obtained through

Table 3
Assumptions considered for the limestone extraction and transportation (Bendouma et al., 2020).

Process	Assumptions		
Limestone extraction	Diesel consumption for extraction	0.36	l/t limestone extracted
	Groundwater	0.45	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Surface water evaporation	8.12×10^{-3}	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Groundwater evaporation	2.12×10^{-2}	m ³ /t limestone extracted
	Electricity	2.17	kWh/t limestone extracted
Limestone transportation	Transportation mode	Truck-trailer	Euro 5
	Fuel used for transportation	Diesel	
	Fuel consumption for transportation	2.58	l/t limestone transported
	Distance	100	km

Fig. 2. System boundaries for the investigated scenarios.

Table 4
Assumptions considered for the CaL-based CO₂ capture unit (De Lena et al., 2024).

Process	Assumptions			
CaL capture system	Operating hours	8000	h/year	
	Location	Downstream of the Steel plant, after the flue gas treatment.		
	Total CO ₂ entering the CaL plant	27.8 - 36.0	t CO ₂ /h	
	CO ₂ to storage	25.5 - 34.48	t CO ₂ /h	
	Net electricity produced ^a	-2.56 - 1.34	MW _e	
	Limestone make-up	3.1 - 13.1	t/h	
	Oxygen required	13.1 - 17.4	t/h	
	Ca(OH) ₂ injection for the advanced cases	7.8 - 7.9	t/h	
	Residual forestry biomass is considered to be used as fuel in the calciner with a LHV of 17.74 MJ/kg wet biomass.			
	Biomass ultimate analysis			
	wt.% dry basis			
C	51.00			
H	5.80			
N	0.90			
O	38.21			
S	0.04			
Ash	4.05			
Moisture	10.00			
Landfill disposal was assumed for the solid waste in the STD cases, while the purge is used to produce Ca(OH) ₂ and recirculated back to the carbonator, in the ADV cases.				
Air Separation Unit (ASU)	The O ₂ required for combustion in the calciner is supplied by a cryogenic ASU, with a specific energy consumption of 638 kWh per ton of O ₂ produced.			

^a A positive value indicates surplus electricity that can be exported from the CaL plant, while a negative value signifies the need to import electricity to meet the auxiliary power demand.

Table 5
Assumptions considered for the CO₂ transportation (SCCS - Scottish Carbon Capture and Storage, 2025).

Process	Assumptions		
CO ₂ transportation onshore by pipelines (T1)	Onshore transportation distance via pipelines	20	km
	CO ₂ losses (pipelines, compressors)	0.01	%
CO ₂ transportation onshore by trucks (T2)	Onshore transportation distance via trucks	20	km
	Electricity for CO ₂ liquefaction	0.07	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	Truck capacity	38	t
CO ₂ transportation offshore by ships (T1 and T2)	CO ₂ pressure in truck	19	bar
	Offshore shipping transportation distance	800	km
	Liquefaction energy consumption (only for T1)	0.075	kWh/kg CO ₂ transported
	Boil-off rate ^a	9.93	g CO ₂ /kg CO ₂ transported
	Heavy fuel consumption	1374	t/year

^a The CO₂ emissions associated with boil-off in ship transport result from the gradual heating of the storage tank, primarily due to engine operation and auxiliary processes onboard the ship. As the temperature rises, the pressure of CO₂ increases, and controlled venting becomes imperative to avert the accumulation of excessive pressure within the tank. The release of the vaporized CO₂ is therefore essential to maintain safe pressure levels within the tank.

direct measurements, and secondary data sourced from process simulations, scientific publications, and modelling tools. In particular, the flue gas characteristics adopted in the present analysis, including flow rate, composition, and temperature, were measured at an EAF steel-making plant located in Norway (SWERIM, 2024). Where direct data acquisition was not feasible, validated secondary sources were utilized. On-site measurements were carried out whenever possible to enhance the accuracy of model calibration. An iterative verification process was employed to identify and address data discrepancies. The resulting dataset demonstrates high quality and is deemed representative in terms of technological relevance and resource supply chain coverage. Detailed life cycle inventory (LCI) datasets corresponding to the main CaL-based process, limestone extraction and transportation, as well as the onshore and offshore transport of CO₂, are included in the Supplementary Material file.

The present study employed Sphera®'s LCA for Experts (version 10.8) to perform the environmental assessment, utilizing the ReCiPe 2016 life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method, following the hierarchist cultural perspective. In addition, considering the objective and scope of the current analysis, the following midpoint impact categories are considered appropriate and have been included in the evaluation: Global Warming Potential (GWP), Freshwater Eutrophication Potential (FEP), Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP), Fossil Depletion Potential (FDP), Mineral Depletion Potential (MDP), Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem (POFP_{ecosystem}), Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human health (POFP_{human-health}), Human Toxicity Potential cancer (HTP_{cancer}), Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer (HTP_{non-cancer}), Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential (FETP), and Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (TETP) (Huijbregts et al., 2017).

3. Results and discussions

The LCA results for all investigated scenarios – comprising a steel-making plant integrated with standard (STD) and advanced (ADV) CaL-based configurations – are presented in Table 6, reflecting the previously stated assumptions and constraints.

As presented in Table 6, the environmental assessment includes eight scenarios combining different CaL configurations and CO₂ transportation pathways. The CaL systems are classified as either STD or ADV, each further subdivided based on the presence of intermediate solid storage: NST (no intermediate solid storage) and 2ST (two intermediate solid storage tanks). In addition, two CO₂ transport scenarios are evaluated: T1, which involves onshore pipeline transport followed by offshore shipping, and T2, which includes onshore transport by trucks and offshore shipping. It is important to note that all environmental impact categories are reported per ton of CO₂ captured. This ensures a consistent and fair basis for comparison against other relevant references and across all examined scenarios.

A comparison with previously published studies indicates that the GWP associated with the CaL NST-STD scenario is consistent in magnitude with the results reported by Chisalita et al. (2019). The observed discrepancies can be attributed to differences in the steel production route (EAF in the present study vs. BF-BOF in literature), as well as to the application of different LCIA methods (ReCiPe, 2016 vs. CML, 2001). Furthermore, when compared with amine-based carbon capture applied in steelmaking, CaL exhibits superior environmental performance relative to the MDEA-based reactive gas-liquid system reported by Luca and Petrescu (2021), with the performance gap becoming more pronounced under advanced scenarios.

When comparing the STD and ADV cases, a considerable reduction in the GWP indicator is observed. This reduction is mainly due to the recirculation of the vent gases resulting in the CPU, no longer being released into the atmosphere in the ADV cases, and also the use of Ca(OH)₂ in the carbonator, which increases the CO₂ capture rate. While the GWP is significantly reduced, slight increases are observed in other environmental impact categories, namely FDP, MDP, POFP_{ecosystem},

Fig. 3. CO₂ transportation scenarios considered in the investigated cases.

Table 6
LCA results for the CaL-based system applied to the iron and steel industry.

KPI	Units	NST-STD		2ST-STD		NST-ADV		2ST-ADV	
		T1	T2	T1	T2	T1	T2	T1	T2
GWP	kgCO ₂ eq./tCO ₂ captured	109.66	118.89	106.91	116.13	31.81	41.03	33.43	42.65
FDP	kg _{oil} eq./tCO ₂ captured	11.00	11.68	11.20	11.88	12.95	13.63	13.19	13.87
FETP × 10	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	2.01	2.01	1.92	1.93	1.79	1.80	1.69	1.70
FEP × 10 ³	kg _P eq./tCO ₂ captured	5.29	5.30	5.05	5.06	4.69	4.70	4.42	4.43
HTP _{cancer} × 10	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	7.89	7.88	7.64	7.64	7.22	7.21	6.96	6.95
HTP _{non-cancer}	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	81.36	81.58	77.90	78.12	72.63	72.85	68.57	68.79
MDP × 10	kg _{Cu} eq./tCO ₂ captured	2.91	2.95	3.56	3.60	15.93	15.97	16.45	16.49
POFP _{ecosystem} × 10 ²	kg _{NOx} eq./tCO ₂ captured	2.16	9.03	2.32	9.19	5.08	11.96	5.26	12.14
POFP _{human-health} × 10 ²	kg _{NOx} eq./tCO ₂ captured	2.05	8.91	2.22	9.07	4.95	11.81	5.13	11.99
ODP × 10 ⁵	kg _{CFC-11} eq./tCO ₂ captured	1.63	2.22	1.76	2.35	4.80	5.39	4.98	5.57
TETP	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	3.02	3.17	3.18	3.33	3.80	3.95	4.01	4.17

POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP. These increases are primarily attributed to higher energy demand within the process, as well as an elevated requirement for limestone make-up to ensure sufficient Ca(OH)₂ production from the CaL process purge stream.

A straightforward comparison of the LCA results across the various cases considered in this study is challenging due to the significant variability among environmental indicators. In many instances, a reduction in one indicator is accompanied by an increase in others, complicating a direct evaluation of the overall performance. To facilitate a balanced and comprehensive comparison, normalized plots were developed using the data reported in.

Table 6. To allow for a consistent comparison across environmental impact categories, each indicator was normalized using minimum–maximum scaling. This means that, for each category, the values were rescaled to a range between 0 and 1, where 0 corresponds to the lowest value observed among all cases, and 1 corresponds to the highest impact. The normalized outcomes for the standard and advanced configurations are presented in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. In each scenario, a polygon was constructed by linking the scaled values of the environmental indicators, enabling visual comparison of the aggregated environmental impact. The area enclosed by each polygon reflects the overall environmental burden, with smaller areas indicating superior

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of the environmental performance of the standard CaL cases. a) no intermediate solid storage, b) two intermediate solid storages, S – polygon surface.

Fig. 5. Comparative analysis of the environmental performance of the advanced CaL cases. a) no intermediate solid storage, b) two intermediate solid storages, S – polygon surface.

performance.

Among all scenarios, the 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration demonstrated the lowest overall environmental impact (i.e., with a polygon surface area of 0.7839), indicating superior performance across the evaluated indicators. In contrast, the NST-ADV-T2 configuration exhibited the highest cumulative impact (i.e., surface area of 1.5410), making it the least environmentally favorable scenario, followed closely by the NST-STD-T2 (i.e., surface area of 1.4826).

The following section presents a detailed evaluation of the key sub-systems that contribute the most in each environmental impact category, for the best performing scenario (i.e., 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration). This evaluation aims to highlight the dominant environmental burden sources within the system boundaries and identify potential areas for further improvement.

3.1. Global warming potential (GWP) environmental indicator

Fig. 6 provides a detailed breakdown of the GWP indicator, highlighting the key contributing sub-processes: the limestone supply chain, CaL-based CO₂ capture, and CO₂ transportation. In the 2ST-ADV-T1 scenario, CO₂ transportation exerts the highest influence on the GWP, accounting for 56.39% of the total impact value of 33.43 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. The other two sub-processes have lesser contributions. Accordingly, the CaL system contributes with a share of 28.51% (i.e., 9.53

kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured). The limestone supply chain accounts for the lowest share of the GWP, representing 15.09% (i.e., 5.04 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured). A deeper examination of the CO₂ transportation stage reveals three distinct components: the onshore segment, involving pipeline transport, CO₂ liquefaction at the harbor, and the offshore shipment. The majority of the emissions are attributed to the offshore shipping phase, which contributes approximately 16.84 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. The primary emission sources are the combustion of heavy fuel and the venting of vaporized CO₂ to avert the accumulation of unsafe pressure within storage tanks during transit. The onshore transportation by pipelines generates about 0.10 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. Additionally, the electricity required for the CO₂ liquefaction at the port generates approximately 1.91 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. The limestone extraction provides 1.92 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured, while the transportation phase contributes by 3.12 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. The flue gas to stack from the CaL system results in approximately 3.61 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. This relatively low value is attributed to the recirculation of vent gases from the CO₂ purification unit and the use of Ca(OH)₂ as a sorbent in the polishing zone, which together enable an overall CO₂ capture efficiency of nearly 98.5%. The net electricity consumption of the CaL system amounts to 2.56 MWe, resulting in a GWP of about 1.91 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. This impact arises from four main sub-processes. While the CaL system produces a gross electricity output of 16.62 MWe, corresponding to 0.48 MWh./tCO₂ captured (i.e., electricity available for export), it

Fig. 6. GWP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

generates a negative value for the GWP (i.e., $-11.69 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$). Electricity demand from the ASU (i.e., $0.31 \text{ MWh.}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$), CPU (i.e., $0.14 \text{ MWh.}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$), and CaL (i.e., $0.12 \text{ MWh.}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$) units accounts for $7.40 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, $3.40 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, and $2.79 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, respectively. The required electricity is assumed to be supplied by the national power grid. According to the Sphera LCA database (Sphera, 2024), the national grid mix consists primarily of hydropower (91.60%), wind (7.47%), fuel oil (0.25%), waste-to-energy (0.24%), natural gas (0.19%), photovoltaics (0.11%), coal gases (0.09%), hard coal (0.03%), and biomass (0.02%). At the end of the process, solid residues that are not recirculated are sent to landfill, bringing an additional $4.01 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ to the overall GWP impact.

3.2. Fossil depletion potential (FDP) environmental indicator

Fig. 7 presents the contribution of individual sub-processes to the total value of the FDP indicator, which quantifies the consumption of fossil resources. For the 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration, the total FDP amounts to $13.19 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The transportation of the captured CO_2 ranks as the primary contributor, accounting for 80.49% of the total environmental impact, while the CaL process and the limestone supply chain contribute by 11.22% and 8.29%, respectively. Within the CO_2 transportation phase, which alone is responsible for $10.62 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, the electricity required for CO_2 liquefaction at the port generates $0.25 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, while the offshore shipping stage accounts for approximately $10.37 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ of the total FDP indicator value. The CaL system generates $1.48 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. Of this contribution, the net electricity consumption accounts for $0.26 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, while the disposal of solid waste contributes with $1.22 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. Regarding the limestone supply chain, which generates a total of $1.09 \text{ kg}_{\text{oil eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, approximately 15.6% originates from limestone extraction, whereas 84.4% is attributed to its transportation.

3.3. Freshwater ecotoxicity potential (FETP) environmental indicator

The FETP indicator represents the potential harm that toxic compounds may pose to aquatic ecosystems. In the case of the 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration, the total FETP value is calculated at $0.17 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, as shown in Fig. 8. When analyzing the contribution of the main sub-systems on the FETP environmental indicator, the CaL system accounts for about 96.27%, which represents the highest contribution. The

CO_2 transportation is responsible for 3.36%, while the limestone supply chain has a much lower contribution (i.e., 0.37%). From the CaL process, the wastewater treatment process is the main contributor to the FETP indicator, generating about $0.16 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The solid waste disposal and net electricity have significantly lower contributions (i.e., 5.43×10^{-4} and $0.17 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$). Regarding the transportation of CO_2 , the offshore shipping has the highest impact and it is followed by the energy used for CO_2 liquefaction at the port (i.e., $5.67 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ and $1.59 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, respectively).

3.4. Freshwater eutrophication potential (FEP) environmental indicator

The FEP environmental indicator reflects the accumulation of nutrients, primarily nitrogen and phosphorous, in freshwater ecosystems. Fig. 9 provides a detailed breakdown of the sub-processes that make up the FEP value for the 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration. With a total value of $4.42 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{\text{P eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, the CaL system ranks first with 99.42%, followed by the limestone supply chain, accounting for 0.34%. Lastly, the CO_2 transportation phase has the smallest contribution of only 0.24%. Fig. 9 illustrates that the wastewater treatment sub-process is the primary contributor to the FEP indicator, generating $4.39 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{\text{P eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$.

3.5. Human toxicity potential cancer (HTP_{cancer}) environmental indicator

The HTP_{cancer} impact category quantifies the potential harm of different substances in regard to cancer disease. Fig. 10 shows the distribution of the HTP_{cancer} indicator in the case of 2ST-ADV-T1 scenario, with a total score of $0.70 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. The overall contribution of the CaL being around 95.66%. Of this, the main contribution is observed to be the wastewater treatment process inside the CaL sub-process, with a value of $0.64 \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$, while the electricity consumption and solid waste disposal present significantly lower influences (i.e., $2.16 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ and $1.08 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$). The second sub-process, which contributes to the HTP_{cancer} indicator, is the CO_2 transportation step, with 4.21%, thus generating $2.93 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$. This is divided into two sections, CO_2 liquefaction and offshore shipping, each contributing with a different score to the total impact (i.e., $2.05 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$ and $0.88 \times 10^{-2} \text{ kg}_{1,4\text{-DB eq.}}/\text{t}_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ captured}}$). When looking at the limestone supply chain, a considerably smaller contribution is observed, as it accounts for about 0.13% of the total value of the HTP_{cancer}.

Fig. 7. FDP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Fig. 8. FETP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Fig. 9. FEP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

3.6. Human toxicity potential non-cancer (HTP_{non-cancer}) environmental indicator

Similar to the HTP_{cancer} indicator, the HTP_{non-cancer} refers to the potential harm of different substances to human toxicity, but without causing cancer. As presented in Fig. 11, the total value of the HTP_{non-cancer} for the 2ST-ADV-T1 case is 68.57 kg_{1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured}. The main contribution (i.e., 65.71 kg_{1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured}) comes from the wastewater treatment step, as part of the CaL sub-process. In addition, of the total value of the HTP_{non-cancer}, the CO₂ transportation represents about 3.32%, of which the offshore shipping ranks as the main contributor with approximately 2.26 kg_{1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured}. Moreover, the limestone extraction and transportation accounts for 3.92 × 10⁻² kg_{1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured} and 0.29 kg_{1,4-DB eq./tCO₂ captured}, respectively.

3.7. Mineral depletion potential (MDP) environmental indicator

The impact of the 2ST-ADV-T1 CaL scenario on the reduction of ore grades is quantified by the MDP indicator. As presented in Fig. 12, the total value of the MDP indicator in the considered case is 1.65 kg_{Cu eq./tCO₂ captured}.

tCO₂ captured. From the total score, the CaL CO₂ capture sub-process accounts for about 99.10%, while the CO₂ transportation ranks second with 0.52%, followed by the limestone supply chain with 0.38%. Within the CaL CO₂ capture, the solid waste disposal stands as the primary contributor, generating 1.62 kg_{Cu eq./tCO₂ captured}. All solid emissions from the CaL unit consist of ash/dust separated by the bag filters, thus the disposal of these mineral-containing solids without recovery constitutes the main contribution. The electricity demand for the CaL accounts for 5.91 × 10⁻³ kg_{Cu eq./tCO₂ captured} of the total impact. All of the other sub-processes present significantly lower contributions, generating less than 5.63 × 10⁻³ kg_{Cu eq./tCO₂ captured}.

3.8. Photochemical ozone formation potential ecosystem (POFP_{ecosystem}) environmental indicator

The POFP_{ecosystem} environmental indicator corresponds to the process implication to increase the ozone concentration at the troposphere level, measured in NO_x equivalents to air. The distribution of the POFP_{ecosystem} indicator for the 2ST-ADV-T1 case is presented in Fig. 13. The total value amounts to 5.26 × 10⁻² kg_{NO_x eq./tCO₂ captured}, with the

Fig. 10. HTP_{cancer} indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Fig. 11. HTP_{non-cancer} indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

limestone supply chain and CaL-based sub-process contributing comparably (i.e., 39.02% and 37.52%, respectively), followed by CO₂ transportation, which accounts for 23.47% of the impact. With the CO₂ transportation-related contribution to the POFP_{ecosystem}, offshore shipping accounts for 1.16×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured, while the energy demand associated with CO₂ liquefaction at the port contributes an additional 7.63×10^{-4} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured. Within the limestone supply chain, the transportation stage generates 2.03×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured, whereas the contribution from the extraction phase is significantly lower, amounting to 2.28×10^{-4} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured.

3.9. Photochemical ozone formation potential human-health (POFP_{human-health}) environmental indicator

Similarly, the POFP_{human-health} indicator reflects the potential increase in tropospheric ozone concentration, yet with impacts on human health rather than the ecosystem. A similar distribution pattern is observed, with a total impact of the POFP_{human-health} for the 2ST-ADV-T1 scenario of 5.13×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured (see Fig. 14). The limestone supply chain accounts for the largest share (i.e., 39.78%), followed by the CaL sub-process (i.e., 37.98%), and CO₂ transportation (i.e.,

22.24%). POFP_{human-health} impacts are predominantly driven by limestone transportation (i.e., 2.02×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured), solid waste disposal (i.e., 1.87×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured), and offshore shipping activities (i.e., 1.07×10^{-2} kgNO_x eq./tCO₂ captured).

3.10. Stratospheric ozone depletion potential (ODP) environmental indicator

Fig. 15 presents the distribution of the ODP impact indicator in the case of 2ST-ADV-T1, with a total value of 4.98×10^{-5} kgCFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured. The ODP environmental indicator refers to stratospheric ozone layer depletion associated with anthropogenic emissions to air. Of the total score, limestone supply chain ranks first with the highest contribution (95.57%), followed by CO₂ transportation (2.73%), and CaL-based sub-process (1.70%). An analysis of the limestone supply chain indicates that the majority of emissions are generated during the extraction phase, contributing approximately 4.55×10^{-5} kgCFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured. In comparison, CO₂ transportation results in a cumulative ODP of approximately 1.36×10^{-6} kgCFC-11 eq./tCO₂ captured.

Fig. 12. MDP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Fig. 13. POFPecosystem indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

3.11. Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (TETP) environmental indicator

The distribution of the TETP impact indicator associated with the 2ST-ADV-T1 case is shown in Fig. 16. This indicator reflects the potential impact on terrestrial ecosystems. The total value of the TETP indicator for the investigated process is about 4.01 kg_{1,4-DB} eq./tCO₂ captured. The largest contribution comes from the CO₂ transportation process with 76.33%. The CaL sub-system accounts for about 17.02%, while the limestone supply chain has a lower contribution, 6.65%. When closely evaluating the CO₂ transportation phase, the offshore transportation by ships generates about 2.78 kg_{1,4-DB} eq./tCO₂ captured, followed by the liquefaction process with 0.29 kg_{1,4-DB} eq./tCO₂ captured. The other subprocesses generate a total of 0.94 kg_{1,4-DB} eq./tCO₂ captured, which represents less than 23.5% of the total impact.

Given the strong influence of electricity supply on environmental outcomes, an EU-average electricity grid mix was additionally considered to enhance the general applicability of the LCA results and to enable comparison with a more carbon-intensive energy system. The assumed EU-average electricity grid mix is composed of nuclear (26.64%), natural gas (15.48%), hard coal (14.17%), hydropower

(11.55%), lignite (9.96%), wind (9.38%), photovoltaic (3.18%), biomass (2.82%), biogas (2.06%), fuel oil (1.89%), waste-to-energy (1.36%), coal gases (0.95%), and geothermal (0.20%). A comparison of the environmental performance of the most favorable scenario (2ST-ADV-T1), assuming electricity supply from both Norway and EU-average grid mix, respectively, is reported in Table 7.

The results demonstrate that the electricity mix is a key driver of the environmental performance of CaL-based CO₂ capture integrated into steel production. Substituting the hydropower-dominated Norwegian grid with the more fossil-intensive EU-average mix leads to increase impacts across most assessed categories, highlighting the significant role of upstream electricity-related emissions in shaping overall environmental results.

The most pronounced variations are observed for climate- and fossil-related indicators. Specifically, the GWP increases from 33.43 to 77.44 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured (approximately a 2.3-fold rise), while FDP exhibits an even larger increase, from 13.19 to 35.23 kg_{oil} eq./tCO₂ captured (around 2.7-fold). Substantial increases are also reported for additional indicators, including POFP (for both ecosystem and human health) and TETP, which rises from 4.01 to 12.02 kg_{1,4-DB} eq./tCO₂ captured.

Fig. 14. POFP_{human-health} indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Fig. 15. ODP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

By contrast, FETP and FEP display only marginal differences between the two electricity supply scenarios, while HTP cancer and non-cancer show a slight reduction. Overall, these results indicate that conclusions derived under low-carbon electricity conditions, such as those characteristic of Norway, may not be directly transferable to regions relying on more carbon-intensive power systems, underscoring the importance of accounting for regional electricity mixes when evaluating and comparing the environmental performance of CaL-based CO₂ capture technologies.

4. Conclusions

This paper evaluates, via a cradle-to-gate LCA analysis, the environmental impact of different CaL configurations integrated into an EAF-steel plant in the Mo i Rana region, Norway.

The LCA conducted in this study examines four distinct CaL configurations:

- i) NST-STD – No intermediate storage, standard setup;

- ii) 2ST-STD – Two intermediate storages, standard setup;
- iii) NST-ADV – No intermediate storage, advanced setup;
- iv) 2ST-ADV – Two intermediate storages, advanced setup.

In the standard configurations (STD), neither the Ca(OH)₂ injection nor the recirculation of vent gas from the CPU is considered. On the contrary, the advanced configurations (ADV) include both. Each CaL scenario was assessed in combination with one of two CO₂ transportation scenarios:

- a. T1: Onshore pipeline followed by offshore shipping;
- b. T2: Onshore transportation by truck followed by offshore shipping.

This approach led to eight combined scenarios: NST-STD-T1, NST-STD-T2, 2ST-STD-T1, 2ST-STD-T2, NST-ADV-T1, NST-ADV-T2, 2ST-ADV-T1, 2ST-ADV-T2.

The comparison between the STD and ADV configurations reveals a significant reduction – over 63% – in GWP for the ADV cases. This substantial improvement is primarily driven by the use of Ca(OH)₂,

Fig. 16. TETP indicator distribution for the CaL 2ST-ADV-T1 case.

Table 7

LCA comparison results for the 2ST-ADV-T1 configuration based on electricity source.

KPI	Units	Electricity source	
		Norway grid mix	EU-average mix
GWP	kgCO ₂ eq./tCO ₂ captured	33.43	77.44
FDP	kg _{oil} eq./tCO ₂ captured	13.19	35.23
FETP × 10	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	1.69	1.73
FEP × 10 ³	kg _P eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.42	4.63
HTP _{cancer} × 10	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	6.96	6.87
HTP _{non-cancer}	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	68.57	67.48
MDP × 10	kg _{Cu} eq./tCO ₂ captured	16.45	17.26
POFP _{ecosystem} × 10 ²	kg _{NOx} eq./tCO ₂ captured	5.26	10.10
POFP _{human-health} × 10 ²	kg _{NOx} eq./tCO ₂ captured	5.13	9.90
ODP × 10 ⁵	kg _{CFC-11} eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.98	6.76
TETP	kg _{1,4-DB} eq./tCO ₂ captured	4.01	12.02

which significantly increases CO₂ capture efficiency, as well as by the recirculation of vent gases from the CPU back to the carbonator. Nevertheless, the ADV configurations also exhibit increased impacts in several other categories, including FDP, MDP, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, ODP, and TETP. These increases are largely due to the higher energy demand and the increased consumption of limestone for producing sufficient Ca(OH)₂ from the purge stream.

A comparative analysis of the CO₂ transportation pathways, T1 and T2, reveals that T1 results in higher impacts in five environmental indicators: GWP, HTP_{non-cancer}, POFP_{ecosystem}, POFP_{human-health}, and ODP. Conversely, T1 demonstrates superior performance in six other categories, namely FDP, FETP, FEP, HTP_{cancer}, MDP, and TETP. These findings underscore a clear trade-off between different environmental impacts, emphasizing the need for a balanced evaluation when selecting CO₂ transportation options.

Among all evaluated scenarios, 2ST-ADV-T1 demonstrates the lowest cumulative environmental impact across all indicators. A detailed analysis of sub-process contributions shows that CO₂ transportation accounts for approximately 56.4% of the total GWP, with offshore shipping contributing around 16.8 kgCO₂ eq./tCO₂ captured. This increased score is primarily linked to the fuel burning and release of CO₂ during

transport, a measure necessary to prevent pressure buildup in storage tanks due to rising temperatures onboard the vessel. As a potential mitigation strategy, it is suggested that instead of venting, the released CO₂ could be recompressed and re-liquefied directly on the ship. While this approach would effectively prevent direct emissions, it would also require the installation of additional equipment, thereby increasing vessel weight, energy demand, and fuel consumption. Consequently, a thorough trade-off analysis is essential to determine whether the environmental benefits of avoiding CO₂ release outweigh the additional energy use and emissions. In addition, the economic feasibility of such a strategy must be carefully considered in the decision-making process.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the ADV CaL configurations significantly enhance CO₂ capture efficiency and achieve substantial reductions in GWP. However, these benefits are accompanied by increased impacts in other environmental categories. The selection of the CO₂ transportation option exerts a key role in shaping the overall environmental performance, with each option presenting specific trade-offs across a range of indicators. These findings underscore the necessity of adopting a comprehensive, system-level approach in the design of CCUS-supported pathways, as downstream processes can markedly influence overall environmental outcomes. Such insights are directly relevant for policymakers and industrial stakeholders involved in the development of region-specific decarbonization strategies and infrastructure planning.

Accordingly, improving the efficiency of carbon capture and transportation systems for the steelmaking industry necessitates a thorough evaluation, one that integrates environmental performance across all impact categories with considerations of technical viability and economic factors. Looking ahead, future research should focus on the optimization of integrated systems, exploration and development of alternative CO₂ transportation solutions, as well as the development of strategies aiming to minimize emissions during shipping. Such efforts are essential to support the sustainable decarbonization of the steel-making sector.

Funding

This work has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. Project name: CaLby2030 |

Grant Number: 101075416. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The project is also supported by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alexandru-Constantin Bozonc: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Stefan Cristian Galusnyak:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Letitia Petrescu:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Calin-Cristian Cormos:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project

administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Néstor D. Montiel-Bohórquez:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Elena Catalanotti:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all CaLby2030 project partners for supplying the necessary data sets to complete this work.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2026.148761>.

Nomenclature

NZE	Net Zero Emission Scenario
IEA	International Energy Agency
GHG	Greenhouse gas
BF-BOF	Blast Furnace – Basic Oxygen Furnace
DRI-EAF	Direct Iron Reduction – Electric Arc Furnace
BAT	Best Available Techniques
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage
MEA	Mono-Ethanol-Amine
MDEA	Methyl-Di-Ethanol-Amine
PtG	Power-to-Gas
L/G	Liquid-to-gas
CaL	Calcium Looping
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
CCU	Carbon Capture and Utilization
HM	Hot Metal
CPU	CO ₂ purification unit
ASU	Air Separation Unit
TES	Thermal energy storage
CCR	CO ₂ capture rate
HTF	Heat-transfer fluid
NST	No intermediate solid storage
2ST	Two intermediate solid storages
STD	Standard configuration
ADV	Advanced configuration
CFB	Circulating fluidized bed
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
FU	Functional unit
LHV	Lower heating value
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
GWP	Global Warming Potential
FEP	Freshwater Eutrophication Potential
ODP	Stratospheric Ozone Depletion Potential
FDP	Fossil Depletion Potential
MDP	Mineral Depletion Potential
POFP _{ecosystem}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential ecosystem
POFP _{human-health}	Photochemical Oxidant Formation Potential human health
HTP _{cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential cancer
HTP _{non-cancer}	Human Toxicity Potential non-cancer
FETP	Freshwater Ecotoxicity Potential
TETP	Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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